

Ameliorative Effect of Selenium on Gastrointestinal Damages Following Oral Administration of Indomethacin in Male Wistar Rats

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Abstract

Nonsteroidal anti-inflammatory drugs (NSAIDs) are commonly used for the treatment of pain and inflammation; however, their use is associated with gastrointestinal injury. Selenium, an essential trace mineral involved in several physiological functions, plays an important role in redox balance and possesses antioxidant properties. This study investigated the effect of selenium on gastrointestinal damage following subacute administration of indomethacin. Twenty male Wistar rats weighing 200–250 g were randomly divided into four groups of five rats each. Group 1 served as the control, while Groups 2, 3, and 4 received indomethacin at 5 mg/kg daily. In addition, Groups 3 and 4 received selenium at 2 mg/kg and omeprazole at 20 mg/kg, respectively. All treatments were administered orally for seven days, after which the animals were sacrificed. Blood samples were collected for the determination of TNF- α and NF- κ B levels, while stomach and colon tissues were harvested for the assessment of oxidative stress and antioxidant parameters. The results showed that stomach and colon levels of malondialdehyde (MDA) and hydrogen peroxide (H₂O₂) were significantly increased in the indomethacin-treated group, accompanied by significant reductions in total antioxidant capacity (TAC), superoxide dismutase (SOD), and reduced glutathione (GSH). Administration of selenium and omeprazole significantly reversed these alterations. Similarly, serum levels of TNF- α and NF- κ B were significantly elevated in the indomethacin group compared with the control group, whereas selenium and omeprazole significantly attenuated these increases. Selenium also significantly increased gastric catalase activity compared with the indomethacin-only group. These findings suggest that oral administration of selenium may be beneficial in ameliorating NSAID-induced gastrointestinal oxidative stress, inflammation, and tissue injury.

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Introduction

Gastrointestinal dysfunction comprises of several disorders of the digestive system and these include: gastric ulcer, ulcerative colitis and Crohn's disease (Gileă-Blanariu *et al.*, 2018). These diseases are usually accompanied by oxidative stress and inflammation at the initial stage and can eventually lead to death (Han *et al.*, 2022). Most of these gastrointestinal disorders are caused by the effect of certain substances, which could be food, drugs, gas effluents, pathogens, etc (Shekhar *et al.*, 2025).

Despite the various aetiologies of the gastrointestinal dysfunction, the major cause over the years has been associated with the use of drugs, especially the non-steroidal anti-inflammatory drugs (NSAIDs) (García-Rayado *et al.*, 2018). NSAIDs are a group of drugs, widely used in the treatment of inflammation and pain (Ghlichloo and Gerriets, 2023). However, research has shown that NSAIDs can induce gastrointestinal complications, thereby potentiating their toxicity (García-Rayado *et al.*, 2018) Indomethacin is a

NSAIDs that is capable of causing serious adverse effects in the gastrointestinal system when used in an uncontrolled manner (Domper *et al.*, 2022).

Selenium is an essential trace mineral that is crucial for various bodily functions, including the proper functioning of the immune system (Alamir *et al.*, 2025). It plays a vital role in redox balancing, anti-inflammatory, and antioxidant activities (Bai *et al.*, 2020). It has been reported to help maintain redox balance by neutralizing the reactive oxygen species (ROS) and protecting immune cells from oxidative damage (Guillin *et al.*, 2019). It also exerts anti-inflammatory effects by regulating the production of inflammatory cytokines (Mal'tseva *et al.*, 2022). Moreover, the anti-inflammatory and antioxidant actions of sub-acute orally administered selenium on indomethacin-induced gastrointestinal dysfunction have not been largely defined. This study, therefore, aimed at investigating the ameliorative effect of

selenium on gastrointestinal disorders in male Wistar rats.

Materials and Methods

Chemicals: Indomethacin capsule was purchased from Ningbo DHY Pharma. Co., Ltd., China; Selenium (in the form of sodium selenite) was gotten from Molychem, India; Omeprazole capsule was purchased from Xi'an ZB Biotech Co., Ltd., China.

Experimental Animals: Twenty (20) male Wistar rats aged 8–10 weeks and weighing 200–250 g were obtained from the Department of Physiology, Federal University of Technology, Akure (FUTA), Nigeria, and used for the study. The animals were housed in well-ventilated cages under standard laboratory conditions at the FUTA animal house, maintained on a 12-hour light/dark cycle, and allowed free access to standard rat chow and clean drinking water ad libitum. They were acclimatized for two weeks prior to the commencement of the experiment to ensure adaptation to the laboratory environment. All experimental procedures were performed in accordance with the ARRIVE guidelines, ensuring rigorous and transparent reporting of animal research, including appropriate study design, sample size determination, randomization, blinding, and ethical animal handling. The study adhered strictly to the 3Rs principles (Replacement, Reduction, and Refinement) to promote responsible use of experimental animals. Ethical approval was obtained from the Centre for Research and Development (CERAD), Federal University of Technology, Akure (Approval No: FUTA/ETH/24/136), and all procedures were conducted under institutional animal care standards, including humane handling and euthanasia to minimize animal suffering.

Experimental Design: The animals were randomly allocated into four groups of five rats each ($n = 5$). Group 1 served as the control and received normal saline only. Groups 2, 3, and 4 received indomethacin at a dose of 5 mg/kg prepared in 5% sodium bicarbonate. Group 3 additionally received selenium (sodium selenite - Na_2SeO_3) at 2 mg/kg dissolved in normal saline, while Group 4 received omeprazole at 20 mg/kg prepared in distilled water. All treatments were administered via oral gavage.

Following acclimatization, the animals were fasted for 24 hours before the first administration of indomethacin. Selenium was administered 2 hours after indomethacin in Group 3, while omeprazole was also administered 2 hours post-indomethacin in Group 4. Thereafter, animals had free access to feed and water ad libitum. Treatments were continued daily for 7 consecutive days with the same dosing schedule

(indomethacin followed 2 hours later by either selenium or omeprazole, depending on the group).

On the final day, animals were fasted for 24 hours after the last dose and were subsequently humanely sacrificed.

Collection of Blood and Organs: The stomach and colon were excised and divided into two sections; a section was stored in 2ml of ice cold 0.1M Tris potassium chloride (Tris KCl) buffer, pH 7.4 for biochemical assays. The second section was preserved in buffered formalin for histological analysis. Furthermore, the blood samples were collected through retro-orbital sinus into plain bottles for enzyme linked immunosorbent assay (ELISA). The blood samples were centrifuged at 3000 rpm for 15 minutes to obtain the serum samples.

Biochemical assays: The stomach and colon samples stored in Tris KCl buffer were homogenized and the resultant homogenates were centrifuged at 3000 rpm for 15 minutes. The supernatants post mitochondrial fraction was collected and processed for biochemical experimental procedures.

Determination of Protein concentration: The protein concentrations of the various samples were determined by means of the Biuret method as described by Gornal *et al.*, (1949) with a slight modification of adding potassium iodide to the reagent to prevent precipitation of Cu^{2+} ions as cuprous oxide

Determination of Malondialdehyde levels (MDA): Malondialdehyde (MDA) a marker of lipid peroxidation was determined by measuring the thiobarbituric acid reactive substances (TBARS) produced during lipid peroxidation. This was carried out by the method of Varshney and Kale (1990).

Determination of Total nitrite: Nitrite determination was done using the method described by Ignarro *et al.*, 1987. The assay relies on a diazotization reaction that was originally described by Griess in 1879.

Determination of hydrogen peroxide: Hydrogen peroxide generation was determined according to the method of Wolff, 1994.

Determination of superoxide dismutase activity: The level of SOD activity was determined by the method of Misra and Fridovich (1972).

Determination of Catalase activity: Catalase activity was determined according to the method of Sinha, 1972.

Determination of Reduced Glutathione levels (GSH): The method of Beutler (1963) was followed in estimating the level of GSH.

Determination of Total Antioxidant Capacity :

Total antioxidant capacity was determined according to the method described by Rubio *et al.*, 2016.

Determination of Tumor Necrosis Factor (TNF- α) and Nuclear Factor Kappa B (NF- κ B)

Tumor necrosis factor-alpha (TNF- α) and nuclear factor kappa B (NF- κ B p65) levels were quantified using commercially available enzyme-linked immunosorbent assay (ELISA) kits (Elabscience, USA) according to the manufacturer's instructions, in line with standard high-impact journal protocols for immunoassay-based biomarker analysis. Briefly, serum samples and standards were added to pre-coated microplate wells, followed by incubation with specific biotinylated antibodies and streptavidin HRP conjugate, with successive washing steps to remove unbound reagents. Colour development was achieved using tetramethylbenzidine (TMB) substrate and the reaction was terminated with stop solution, after which absorbance was measured using a microplate reader at 450 nm. Concentrations were determined from standard curves generated for each assay. The assay kits used were TNF- α (Catalogue No: E-EL-R2856) and NF- κ B (Catalogue No: E-EL-R0674).

Statistical Analysis: Data were expressed as mean \pm standard error of the mean (SEM) and analysed using

GraphPad Prism version 9.5. Data normality was assessed using the Shapiro–Wilk test. Statistical comparisons between groups were performed using one-way analysis of variance (ANOVA), followed by Tukey's post hoc multiple comparison test. Differences were considered statistically significant at $p < 0.05$.

Results: Figure 1: Effect of selenium on total protein and malondialdehyde (MDA) concentration in the stomach and colon following indomethacin administration

Figure 1A and 1B represent the total protein concentration in the stomach and colon, respectively. There was no significant difference in the protein concentration across the groups in both organs. The MDA concentration of both the stomach and colon is presented in Figures 1C and 1D, and they were both significantly increased in the Indo 5mg/kg group compared to the control. The MDA concentration was significantly decreased in the Indo 5mg/kg + Sel 2mg/kg group compared to the Indo 5mg/kg group in both stomach and colon samples. The Indo 5mg/kg + Sel 2mg/kg group was significantly increased in the colon compared with the control

Figure 1: Effect of selenium on protein and malondialdehyde (MDA) concentration in the stomach and colon following indomethacin administration (A- Protein concentration of stomach, B- Protein concentration of Colon, C- MDA concentration of stomach, D- MDA concentration of colon): Values are presented as Mean \pm SEM, *Significant difference at $p < 0.05$ compared with control, # significant difference at $p < 0.05$ when compared with Indo 5mg/kg

Figure 2: Effect of selenium on nitric oxide (NO) and hydrogen peroxide (H₂O₂) concentration in the

stomach and colon following indomethacin administration

Figure 2A and 2B represent the effect of selenium on NO concentration in the stomach and colon, respectively. A significant decrease in the NO concentration of the stomach was observed in Indo 5mg/kg compared to the control. However, the NO concentration of the colon was significantly increased in Indo 5mg/kg compared with the control. A significant decrease in the NO concentration of the colon was observed in both Indo 5mg/kg + Sel 2mg/kg and Indo 5mg/kg + Ome 20mg/kg compared to the Indo 5mg/kg group.

The effect of selenium on H₂O₂ concentration in the stomach and colon is shown in Figures 2C and 2D. H₂O₂ concentration was significantly increased in the

Indo 5mg/kg group compared to the control group in both organs. In the stomach (Fig 2C), H₂O₂ concentration was significantly decreased in the Indo 5mg/kg + Sel 2mg/kg group compared with both the Indo 5mg/kg and control groups, respectively; and significantly increased in the Indo 5mg/kg + Ome 20mg/kg group compared with the control group. In the colon sample (Fig 2D), the H₂O₂ concentration was significantly decreased in the Indo 5mg/kg + Ome 20mg/kg group compared with the Indo 5mg/kg group; the concentration of H₂O₂ in the Indo 5mg/kg + Sel 2mg/kg group was significantly increased compared with the control.

Figure 2: Effect of selenium on nitric oxide (NO) and hydrogen peroxide (H₂O₂) concentration in stomach and colon following indomethacin administration (A- Nitric oxide concentration of stomach, B- Nitric oxide concentration of colon, C- H₂O₂ concentration of stomach, D- H₂O₂ concentration of colon)

Values are presented as Mean ± SEM, *Significant difference at p<0.05 compared with control, # significant difference at p<0.05 when compared with Indo 5mg/kg

Figure 3: Effect of selenium on Superoxide Dismutase (SOD) and catalase activity in stomach and colon following indomethacin administration (A- SOD activity of stomach, B- SOD activity of colon, C- Catalase activity of stomach, D- Catalase activity of colon): Values are presented as Mean \pm SEM, *Significant difference at $p < 0.05$ compared with control, # significant difference at $p < 0.05$ when compared with Indo 5mg/kg

The results for SOD activity in the stomach and colon are shown in Figure 3A and 3B, respectively. The activity of SOD was significantly decreased in the Indo 5mg/kg group compared with the control in both organs. In the stomach (Fig 3A), the SOD activity of Indo 5mg/kg + Sel 2mg/kg was significantly increased compared with the control and Indo 5 mg/kg groups, respectively; however, it was significantly decreased in Indo 5mg/kg + Ome 20mg/kg compared with both the control and Indo 5mg/kg groups. The SOD activity of Indo 5mg/kg and Indo 5mg/kg + Sel 2mg/kg groups was significantly decreased in the colon (Fig 3B) compared with the control. The Indo 5mg/kg + Ome 20mg/kg was significantly increased compared with Indo 5mg/kg.

Catalase activity is shown in Figures 3C and 3D. Catalase activity was significantly increased in the selenium group compared to both the control and indomethacin groups in the stomach, while other

groups were insignificant. More so, it was insignificantly increased across all groups in the colon (Fig 3D).

Figure 4A and 4B represent the effect of selenium on reduced glutathione (GSH) in the stomach and colon, respectively. The GSH was significantly decreased in the Indo 5mg/kg group compared with the control in both organs. Moreover, the GSH activity of Indo 5mg/kg + Sel 2mg/kg and Indo 5mg/kg + Ome 20mg/kg groups was significantly increased compared with the Indo 5mg/kg group in both organs.

The TAC, as represented in figures 4C and 4D, was significantly decreased in the Indo 5mg/kg group compared with the control in both the stomach and colon. However, it was significantly increased in the Indo 5mg/kg + Sel 2mg/kg and Indo 5mg/kg + Ome 20mg/kg groups compared with the Indo 5mg/kg group and the control group in both organs

Figure 4: Effect of selenium on Reduced Glutathione (GSH) and Total antioxidant capacity (TAC) in stomach and colon following indomethacin administration (A- GSH of stomach, B- GSH of colon, C- TAC of stomach, D- TAC of colon). Values are presented as Mean ± SEM, *Significant difference at p<0.05 compared with control, # significant difference at p< 0.05 when compared with Indo 5mg/kg

Table 1: Effect of selenium on tumor necrosis factor-alpha (TNF-α) and nuclear factor kappa B (NF-κB) in blood serum following indomethacin administration Table 1 shows the effect of selenium on TNF-α and NF-κB in blood serum following indomethacin administration. Both TNF-α and NF-κB were

significantly increased in the Indo 5mg/kg group compared with the control. However, they were significantly decreased in Indo 5mg/kg + Sel 2mg/kg and Indo 5mg/kg + Ome 20mg/kg groups compared with the Indo 5mg/kg group.

Groups	TNF-a (pg/ml/mg protein)	NF-kB (pg/ml/mg protein)
Control	56.00±6.012	140.00±10.91
Indo 5mg/kg	114.00±10.34*	189.80±12.33*
Indo 5mg/kg + Sel 2mg/kg	58.04±4.01#	117.0±2.20#
Indo 5mg/kg + Ome 20mg/kg	70.56±4.00#	108.40±3.59#

Values are presented as Mean ± SEM, *Significant difference at p<0.05 compared with control, # significant difference at p< 0.05 when compared with Indo 5mg/kg

Discussion

Selenium is a trace element that has been reported to possess anti-inflammatory and antioxidant properties at a low dose (Bai *et al.*, 2020; Kamble *et al.*, 2009). Indomethacin, on the other hand, has been linked to gastrointestinal damages which is characterized by increased ROS and inflammation (Danisman *et al.*, 2023). The increased length and time between doses

are factors responsible for its harmful effect (Davies *et al.*, 1993). Mechanistically, indomethacin-induced mitochondrial dysfunction promotes the formation of superoxide radicals, which are subsequently converted to H₂O₂. When antioxidant defenses become overwhelmed, accumulated H₂O₂ generates highly reactive hydroxyl radicals that initiate lipid peroxidation of cellular membranes, resulting in increased MDA formation. Concurrent depletion of

TAC, SOD, and GSH further indicates impairment of endogenous antioxidant defenses, thereby exacerbating oxidative tissue injury and contributing to the pathogenesis of indomethacin-induced gastrointestinal damage. (Kielczykowska *et al.*, 2018). This was also accompanied by a marked elevation in inflammatory mediators, including TNF- α and NF- κ B, further supporting activation of inflammatory pathways in indomethacin-induced injury. Collectively, these changes reflect a shift toward oxidative stress and inflammatory imbalance in the affected tissues. (Sánchez-Trigueros *et al.*, 2021), and this is due to its ability to induce lipid peroxidation (Mahmoud *et al.*, 2021). The observed reduction in MDA and H₂O₂ levels following selenium treatment may be attributed to its incorporation into antioxidant selenoproteins such as glutathione peroxidases and thioredoxin reductases. These enzymes catalyse the detoxification of reactive oxygen species and lipid hydroperoxides, thereby limiting oxidative damage, preserving membrane integrity, and maintaining cellular redox homeostasis. Selenium may also enhance endogenous antioxidant defenses, including SOD activity and GSH availability, further contributing to its cytoprotective effects (Turkyilmaz *et al.*, 2019).

Total antioxidant capacity (TAC) is a global indicator of the cumulative antioxidant status of biological systems rather than a measure of individual antioxidant enzymes (Bai *et al.*, 2020). The significant reduction in total antioxidant capacity (TAC) in the indomethacin-treated group reflects the overwhelming of endogenous antioxidant defense systems due to excessive reactive oxygen species (ROS) generation. Indomethacin-induced mitochondrial dysfunction and inflammatory activation promote sustained production of superoxide radicals and downstream oxidants such as hydrogen peroxide and hydroxyl radicals. These reactive species continuously consume available non-enzymatic antioxidants (e.g., glutathione, vitamins C and E) and impair enzymatic antioxidants (such as SOD, catalase, and glutathione peroxidase), thereby depleting overall antioxidant reserves. As ROS production exceeds the rate of antioxidant regeneration, cellular redox homeostasis is disrupted, resulting in a net reduction in TAC (Halliwell, 2024). In contrast, selenium supplementation significantly increased TAC, indicating restoration of antioxidant defense capacity. This finding is consistent with reports that selenium enhances antioxidant status through incorporation into selenoproteins that regulate redox balance and detoxify ROS (Angelone *et al.*, 2024; Baladhye *et al.*, 2025). Furthermore, evidence from experimental studies has shown that selenium-

dependent glutathione peroxidase activity is present in the rat gastrointestinal mucosa, supporting the biological plausibility of selenium-mediated mucosal protection. Therefore, the observed protective effect of selenium in this study may be attributed to its ability to enhance mucosal antioxidant defense systems, reduce lipid peroxidation, and suppress inflammatory signalling pathways implicated in indomethacin-induced gastrointestinal injury (Kim *et al.*, 2012).

Nitric oxide (NO) is a multifunctional signalling molecule that plays a dual role in gastrointestinal physiology and inflammation. While physiological concentrations of NO contribute to mucosal defense, vascular homeostasis, and epithelial integrity, excessive NO production, particularly through inducible nitric oxide synthase (iNOS), promotes inflammatory responses and tissue injury (Archontakis-Barakakis *et al.*, 2025). Mechanistically, NO modulates inflammation through complex interactions with the NF- κ B signalling pathway, a key regulator of pro-inflammatory gene expression (Kim and Lee, 2025). Depending on its concentration and cellular redox state, NO may either activate or suppress NF- κ B-mediated inflammatory responses. Furthermore, NO can react with cysteine sulfhydryl (-SH) residues of target proteins, resulting in S-nitrosylation, a post-translational modification capable of altering protein function and attenuating NF- κ B activation (Luo *et al.*, 2024). In pathological conditions, excess NO readily reacts with superoxide anions (O₂⁻) to generate peroxynitrite (ONOO⁻), a highly reactive oxidant that contributes to oxidative damage, lipid peroxidation, and cellular dysfunction (Prolo *et al.*, 2024). Consistent with these mechanisms, the present study demonstrated elevated NO levels in the colon of indomethacin-treated animals, suggesting enhanced nitric oxide mediated stress and inflammatory activity. Conversely, NO levels were reduced in the stomach, which may reflect impairment of its gastroprotective functions, including maintenance of mucosal blood flow, mucus secretion, and epithelial restitution. Selenium supplementation significantly attenuated colonic NO elevation, likely through its antioxidant and anti-inflammatory actions mediated by selenoproteins such as glutathione peroxidases and thioredoxin reductases, which limit reactive oxygen species generation and downstream inflammatory signalling (Kim and Lee, 2025). In the stomach, selenium treatment further modulated NO levels, potentially contributing to preservation of mucosal integrity and protection against indomethacin-induced gastric injury.

Indomethacin induces inflammation by affecting NF- κ B, a protein that is responsible for the expression of

adhesion molecules such as Intercellular Adhesion Molecule 1 (ICAM-1). A pro-inflammatory cytokine known as TNF- α is involved in NSAIDs-induced damage by contributing to the increment of ICAM-1 and thereby potentiating inflammatory response (Silva *et al.*, 2019). More so, it increases intracellular oxidative stress. The findings of this study have shown the effectiveness of selenium in ameliorating damage caused by the actions of the inflammatory cytokine (NF- κ B) (Sinha *et al.*, 2023). This will lead to decreased production of pro-inflammatory cytokines like TNF- α . This aligns with the findings of Mal'tseva and colleagues, in that selenium regulates the activities of inflammatory cytokines through direct oxidation of critical sulfhydryl groups of the transcription factor (Mal'tseva *et al.*, 2022). Moreover, this anti-inflammatory effect could also be a result of the presence of seleno S, a type of selenoprotein responsible for producing anti-inflammatory mediators (Gilcã-Blanariu *et al.*, 2018).

A limitation of this study is the use of serum NF- κ B levels instead of direct tissue assessment. While serum NF- κ B may reflect systemic inflammation, it does not accurately represent localized NF- κ B activation within gastrointestinal tissues, where indomethacin-induced injury primarily occurs. Since NF- κ B functions intracellularly as a transcription factor regulating pro-inflammatory gene expression, its activity is best evaluated at the tissue level.

Therefore, serum measurements may underestimate or indirectly reflect the actual inflammatory signalling occurring at the site of injury and may also be influenced by unrelated systemic inflammatory processes. Future studies should incorporate tissue-based evaluation of NF- κ B using methods such as immunohistochemistry, Western blotting, or gene expression analysis in gastric or intestinal tissues to provide more precise mechanistic insight into NF- κ B-mediated inflammatory pathways.

Conclusion

This study demonstrated that subacute oral administration of indomethacin induced oxidative stress and inflammatory alterations in the gastrointestinal tract of male Wistar rats, as shown by increased MDA, H₂O₂, TNF- α , and NF- κ B levels, together with reduced antioxidant defence markers. Selenium treatment ameliorated these alterations by improving antioxidant status and reducing inflammatory markers. The findings suggest that selenium may possess gastroprotective potential against indomethacin-induced gastrointestinal injury. However, further studies involving histopathological

confirmation, dose-response evaluation, and clearer toxicity assessment are recommended.

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